

Green Human Resource Management Practices and Sustainability: A Review of Literature

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ABSTRACT

Human Resource Management plays an important role and it is the management of people working in the organization. In this current competitive business environment, many HR managers in organization identified and implemented Green Programmes in their work place that can promote the social responsibility among employee's and help to retain the skilled workers. The objective of this conceptual paper is to explain the concept of Green HRM practices and to make a literature review on Green Human Resource Management Practices and Sustainability. The study is based on secondary data. In this review paper, the researcher reviewed 15 studies (online available articles) from the year 2014 to 2018. The result of this study provides a contribution for Green Human Resource Management and Sustainability literature and also for the organizations to invest more Green HRM policies and activities.

1. Introduction

Human Resource Management (HRM) is an art of developing people and their potentialities for their personal and the growth of the organization. In this competitive business environment, organizations are developing new human resource strategies and practices in their HRM functions to attract and retain their skilled employees. Thus the human resource management is the process of acquiring, training developing, motivating and evaluating a sufficient number of employees to perform the activities required for an organizations objective, generation of satisfaction and optimal productivity and effectiveness of employees (Tapomoy Deb, 2009). Hence, HRM is the management of employees of an organization from their recruitment to retirement. In an organization the HR managers has to perform many functions. Out of all the functions, employee recruitment, training and development, employee relation, pay and reward and performance management are the major functions.

2. Objectives of the Study

- To explain the concept of Green HRM practices,
- To discuss the extensive literature on Green HRM practices and Sustainability

3. Research Methodology

The study is primarily based on the secondary data. To discuss the extensive literature on Green HRM practices and Sustainability, the researcher collected data from the 15 existing online published articles on Green HRM practices and Sustainability from the year of 2014 to 2018.

Green Human Resource Management (GHRM)

Many HR managers in organization identify and implemented Green Programmes in their work place that can promote the social responsibility among employee's and help to

retain the skilled workers. In general, organizations have their own environmental policies and practice.

Green Management generally refers to the environmental aspects (Wioletta Skibinska, Iga Kott, 2015). It is the development of personnel responsible for environmental activities, environmental management systems, and environmental communication as well as conservation of biodiversity. The Green HR initiatives also help companies find alternative ways to cut cost without losing their top talent. The HR professionals indicated that encouraging employees to be more environmentally friendly in the workplace was the top practice for their organizations.

Green Human Resource Management (GHRM) has become a key business strategy for every organization. Green Human Resource Management (GHRM) is the use of human resource management policies to promote the sustainable use of resources within the organization and, more generally promote the cause of environment sustainability (Marhatta, 2012). Green HRM is also refers to the policies, practices and systems that make employees of the organization green for the benefit of the individual, society, natural environment and the business (Opatha and A. Arulrajah 2014).

Green Human resource management practices also involves undertaking environment friendly HR initiatives resulting in greater efficiencies, lower cost and better employee engagement and which in turn help the organization to reduce employee carbon.

According to Viola Muster and Ulf Schrader (2015), green HR consists of two elements namely;

- environmentally friendly HR practices and
- preservation of knowledge capital.

Goyal & Dutta (2014). found the various initiatives that can be taken by Government to promote green practices. The study further highlighted the green HR practices are car-pooling, teleconferencing, recycling, online training, e-mailing etc. According to Mandip (2012), Green human resources refer to using every employee touch point/interface to promote sustainable practices and increase employee awareness and commitments on the issues of sustainability.

Similarly, green HRM in organizations involves reducing carbon footprints via less printing of paper, car sharing, job sharing, telecommuting, video conferencing and interviews (Gill Mandip; Shakti, 2012). Green HRM is also a management strategy that for reducing carbon print of employees and talent retention (TulseeGiriGoswami and Saroj Kumar

Ranjan, 2015). Some examples of Green HR activities can be use of job portals of companies for recruitment and the use of telephonic, online and video interviews. This can reduce the travel requirements of the candidates, besides causing reduction in paper work. As part of compensation management, companies can have introduced Green rewards to employees in the form of nature-friendly workplace and lifestyle benefits, which may include carbon credit offsets, free bicycles and pollution-free vehicles for commuting to and in the workplace in order to engage people in the green agenda. These Green human resources management practices support environmental performance of the organization.

The following figure shows the Green Human Resource Management System

(Source: Retika Verma)

Thus, the basic objectives of these Green HRM practices in the organizations are;

- to attract human resources into the organization through Green HRM practices / policies,
- to increase the awareness about Green HRM practices
- to motivate the employees by using Green HRM practices and policies for the better environmental performance of the organization,
- to integrate and maintain them in the organization.

There are well-meaning green HR practices that leading companies have adopted to manage environmental problems. Green HRM functions includes recruitment, training and development, performance appraisal and management, employee relations, pay and reward, and exit (Jacob Cherian and Jolly Jacob, 2012; Mohammad Main Uddin and Rabiul Islam, 2015; Geetu Nijhawan, 2014). Thus the, Green Human Resource Management Practices are the use of human resource management practices and policies such a way to promote sustainable use of resources in business organizations to make eco-friendly. The following table shows the HRM functions and the way of making them Green;

Table-1: Green Human Resource Management Functions

No	Green HRM Functions	Descriptions
1	Green Recruitment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To include environmental criteria in the recruitment messages. • To select applicants who are sufficiently aware of greening to fill job vacancies.
2	Green Training and Development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To impart right knowledge and skills about greening to each employee through a training program exclusively designed for greening
3	Employee Involvement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To encourage employees to make suggestions for green improvements
4	Pay and Reward	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To give financial incentives to employees for their good green performance of job.

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To give non-financial rewards such as praises and recognitions to employees for their greening.
5	Performance Management System	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To evaluate employee's job performance according to green-related criteria. • To include a separate component for progress on greening in the performance feedback interview

(Source: Opatha 2013)

Sustainability

Now a day's organizations are more concerned about environmental sustainability and corporate social responsibility. Sustainable development is really mostly identified by referring to this establishment of a balance between Profit, Planet and People. According to the World Commission on Environment and Development (WCED) Sustainability, or sustainable development, is broadly defined as "development that meets the needs of the present generation without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs". The term Sustainable Development (SD) was used for the first time, at the United Nations Conference on the Human Environment in Stockholm in 1972. Numerous studies prove that corporate sustainability management focused on creating a harmonious relationship with various stakeholders brings a number of benefits to the organisation. Rani. S & Mishra K. (2014) reveals that the HRM policies to promote the sustainable use of resources within business organizations and more generally promotes the cause of environmental sustainability.

Haridas P.K and Chitra Sivasubramanian (2016), in their study also found that there is a positive relationship between Green HRM practices and Sustainability. Parida Ruchimita et al (2015), also identified that Green HRM practices are important part of organizations and also for a sustainable future. Nithya Daimy KM and Edmund Christopher S (2016) noted that the implementation and usage of green environment plans will help the organization to fulfill its goals. Hence, the proper understanding and implementation of green HR practices, a firm can improve its social and organizational performance in a sustainable manner that will create some competitive advantages for them

4. Review of Literature.

A brief review of the various recent studies directly related to Green HRM practices and Sustainability is presented here in chronological order as follows;

Green HRM and Sustainability.

1. Suhaimi Sudin and Zuliawati Mohamed Saad (2018), made a study on Green HRM. The purpose of the study was to explore the relationship between Green HRM, Environmental Management Systems and Corporate Environmental Citizenship Behaviour. The study was conducted in Malaysia and the data for the study collected through questionnaire. The study used regression analysis for analysing the data. The result of the study found that Green HRM practices significantly related to environmental management system. This environmental management system will improve the environmental sustainability.
2. Sasmita Nayak and Vikashita Mohanthy (2017), studied about Green HRM for business sustainability. This

study also states that, the green HRM practices like, green recruitment, green selection, green induction, green performance appraisal, green compensation and reward systems are the powerful tools in making employees eco-friendly for business sustainability.

3. Md. Mamin Ullah (2017), studied about integrating environmental sustainability into human resource management. The main aim of the study was to analyse the concepts, importance, practices and implications of Green Human Resource management. The study was based on the secondary data. The study has found that the green human resource management practices result in expanded efficiencies, economical utilization of resources, less wastage, improved job related attitude, improved work /private life which help organizations to ensure sustainability.
4. Aravind S and Mohanamoj k (2017), studied about green hr: a novel approach to environmental sustainability. This paper discusses the concept of Green HRM. It also covers the path to sustainability through Green HRM practices.
5. Haridas P.K et al (2016), made a study on Green Human Resource management and Sustainability. The main objective of the study was to investigate the impact of Green Human Management Practices on the Environmental Sustainability. The study conducted in Kerala and the primary data were collected by using questionnaire form the IT professionals. The result of the regression analysis showed that the Green HRM practices like green recruitment, green training and development, green employee relations and green compensation have a significant influence on Environmental Sustainability.
6. Benard Langat and Josphat Kwasira (2016), studied the influence of green human resource management practices on environmental sustainability in Kenya. Sample size of the study was 96 employees. The result of the study states that, there is a positive significant relationship between green motivational strategies and environmental sustainability
7. Winnie Achieng Owino and Joseph Kwasira (2016), studied about the Green HRM practices and sustainability. The objective of the study was to analyse the influence of Green HRM practices on environmental sustainability. The study conducted at Menengai Oil Refinery, Kenya. Sample size of the study was 163 employees. The collected data analysed with descriptive and inferential statistics. The result of the study found that, green performance management had a significant influence on environmental sustainability.
8. Bassam K and Mujeeb Rahman AP (2016) made a study on Green HRM-A Tool of Sustainable Development. The purpose of this study is to discuss

the green HRM practice. The study was based on secondary data collected from different sources. The study also revealed that there is relationship between green hrn practices and sustainability.

9. Mehtab-un-Nisa et al (2016), Present study aims to determine the connection between the green human resource factors like management commitment, employee empowerment, feedback & review, rewards and exit with sustainability through environmental management systems implementation. Data were collected through questionnaires. The sample size of the study was 354 employees of thirteen leading manufacturing organizations in Pakistan. Quantitative research methodology and convenience sampling technique were used. Data have been analyzed through descriptive statistics, correlation, and multiple regressions using SPSS. Results prove a significant effect of all GHRM dimensions on sustainability.
10. MousumiSengupta and NilanjanSengupta (2015), studied about green HRM and sustainability. The study was based on both primary and secondary data. The study indicated that the green HRM practice like employee involvement and participation would play a vital role in organizational environmental performance.
11. Saher Sayed (2015), also studied about green HRM and Sustainability. The objective of the study was based on secondary. The study states that, the Green HRM can play a useful role in promoting sustainability by adopting green HR policies and practices.
12. Mohammad Main Uddin and MdRabiul Islam (2015), made study on Green HRM. The objectives of the study were to review the extensive literatures in the Green HRM area and to develop a process model. This study also states that the green HRM practices like recruitment, training and development, performance management and appraisal, employee relations and pay and rewards can play a useful role in promoting environmental related issues.

13. Venkatsh ,Lisst TA and Vaishnavi Bhatt (2014), made a study on Sustainable development and role of HRM . The study conducted in Indian IT industries. The study used factor analysis method. The result of the study states that, the variables like employee autonomy, training and development and E-HRM programs ply am important role in organizations sustainable development.
14. K.Kiruthigaa and MiniViswanathan (2014) studied about awareness of green recruitment. The study was based on both primary and secondary data. Sample size of the study was 100.The result of the study reveals that, there is a positive impact on green recruitment on sustainable development.
15. Geethu Nijhawan (2014), made a study on Green HRM. The study reveals that the various green HRM practices like green recruitment, green training and development, green performance management, green compensation, green employee relation and exit have been important role in the organizations long term sustainability.

5. Conclusion

Green Human Resource Management practices is an emerging trend and many organizations have designed environmental concerned HRM practices. The literature reveals that the practices of Green HRM includes compensation, recruitment and selection, performance management, training and development, employee involvement and participation and these practices can improve the environmental performance of the organization. To conclude, the sustainable development and organization environmental performance a can be maintained by different Green HRM practices and policies.

Figure-1: Green HRM Model

(Source: Author generated)

So, all the HR managers must make both individuals and the organizations to be aware of Green concept and Green

HRM practices and take necessary actions towards knowing the importance of it and working towards it.

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